

EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF CLOMIPRAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE CONTAINING NASAL SPRAY FOR THE PHARMACOTHERAPY OF PREMATURE EJACULATION.

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Introduction & Objectives: The aim of the study is to evaluate the efficacy and safety of nasal spray, containing Clomipramine hydrochloride (Cl spray) in the treatment of men with premature ejaculation (PE).

Materials & methods: The single blinded, randomized, placebo controlled, parallel trial included 46 heterosexual men (mean age 34years) who had stable monogamous sexual relations and self-reported intravaginal ejaculation latency time (IELT) of less than 2 minutes during the period at the least 6 last month. The clinical study has been approved by institutional ethical committee. The underwent assessment in accordance with International Society for SEXUAL MEDICINE guidelines. After two week washout period men were randomized to receive either single dose 4mg nasal CL spray (N=19), or nasal placebo spray (N=15), in daily regimen at 5 hours before usual time of intercourse. Patients were prospectively followed for 8 weeks. Every 4th week of treatment patient condition was assessed by self-reported IELT, fill in questionnaire Uzbek Index of Premature Ejaculation (UIPE) and International Index of Erectile Function-5 (IIEF-5). The primary endpoints were the self-reported IELT and UIPE score; secondary endpoints include IIEF-5 score and adverse effects of the drug.

Results. The trial was completed by 33 (97%) men. The mean IELT increased from pre-treatment values of 28.5+22.1 and 32.4+24.7 seconds to 142.2+76.5 and 41.7+38.3 seconds post treatment respectively for CL spray and placebo (P<0.05 for treatment group), baseline mean UIPE scores 25.4+7.5 and 27.5 + 8.5 reached to 15.1+7.2 and 16.0 + 5.8 at 8 week treatment for CL spray and placebo respectively (P<0.05 for treatment group). The difference between initial and post-treatment IIEF-5 values in both groups were statistically insignificant (32.5+1.5 and 32.5+1.0 vs 31.6+3 and 32+0.6 in main and placebo groups, respectively, P>0.05). The most common observed side effect was nasal irritation in 3 patients in CL spray and 1 patient in placebo group, but it was

transient and well tolerated. The other adverse effects occurred in 2 patients of CL group were dry mouth and headache.

Conclusions: This study showed that CL spray was more efficacious than placebo and well tolerated. The common adverse reactions were mild and self-limited. Further studies with different groups of patients are necessary to draw final conclusions on the efficacy and safety of CL spray in PE.

